

Growth and Formation of Perovskite Nanocrystals and Their Superstructures Revealed by In-situ Spectroscopy

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ABSTRACT: Metal halide perovskites have attracted substantial interest due to their promising properties for optoelectronic applications. Despite much progress made in the field, the exact growth mechanism of perovskite nanocrystals (*e.g.* CsPbBr₃) remains elusive and further improvement of their controllable synthesis is challenging. Herein, we reveal different stages during growth and purification of high-quality CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals using in-situ PL spectroscopy and the as-synthesized materials are further characterized by using time-resolved transient differential transmission and photoluminescence spectroscopy. Remarkably, nanocrystals form superstructures already during synthesis, which is confirmed by X-ray spectroscopy. The formation process can be explained by a model based on self size selection. On the one hand, such superstructures may be useful for high-quality devices such as LEDs. On the other hand, the approach to reveal their formation process can be adopted for various other material systems.

KEYWORDS Perovskite nanocrystals, CsPbBr₃, hot-injection, superstructure, growth mechanism

1. Introduction

Metal halide perovskites (*e.g.*, CH₃NH₃PbX₃, CsPbX₃, X = Cl, Br, I) have attracted emerging attention in the last decade due to their promising performance in optoelectronic and photonic applications,¹⁻³ including light-emitting devices (LEDs),⁴⁻⁷ solar cells^{8,9} and photodetectors.^{10,11} Especially, the nanocrystal of perovskites, compared to their bulk ones, have exhibited a more significant potential in practical uses. For example, they possess outstanding properties including a near-unity photoluminescence quantum yield (PL QY), a narrow emission bandwidth, a precisely tunable emission wavelength, a facile synthetic method and a high tolerance towards structural defects and surface states regarding the optical and electronic properties.^{3,12-14} The first synthesis

of $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbBr}_3$ nanocrystals (NCs) was developed utilizing an Al_2O_3 template.¹⁵ Since then, methods such as precipitation, hot-injection and sonication have been developed in the field. Nowadays, a well-established hot-injection method allows the preparation of high-quality NCs,¹⁶⁻²⁴ especially all-inorganic CsPbX_3 perovskites, with various morphologies including nanorods, nanowires, and nanoplatelets.^{20, 25-33} Although enormous progress has been made in the synthesis, the detailed formation mechanism of metal halide perovskite NCs stays unclear owing to its rather low formation energy and a fast crystallization rate, which are challenging to characterize and analyze. Some studies have attempted to discuss the synthetic mechanism of perovskite nanocrystals. For example, a microfluidic flow reactor platform has been previously reported to inspect the formation process of CsPbX_3 NCs and to optimize the synthetic parameters.³⁴ However, there is still a lack of systematic investigation of multiple factors, such as the formation process, cooling process and purification process, which altogether govern the stepwise growth of CsPbBr_3 NCs during wet chemical synthesis. Such missing fundamental information remains the key to the rational design of the desired high-quality synthesis, instead of endless trial-and-error procedures. Hence, it is significantly meaningful and urgently needed to reveal the growth mechanism of perovskite nanocrystals using cutting-edge spectroscopies.

Besides the mechanism of how perovskite NCs are synthesized, another challenging topic is the mechanism of how NCs assemble to form their superstructure, perovskite supercrystals (SCs), which leads to an electronic coupling between individual NCs.³⁵ Such superstructure is of particular interest since it may cause a miniband formation in both valence and conduction bands, which results in a redshift of the PL.^{36,37} It is challenging to prove the existence of SCs in solutions. Despite significant advances in the self-assembly of metal and conventional semiconductor NCs into one-dimensional (1D), 2D, and 3D superlattices, the realization of self-assembled perovskite

NCs has hardly been reported so far.^{36,37} However, taking advantage of an in-situ detection method, such a formation could be monitored.

In this work, we reveal different stages of the hot-injection synthesis of perovskite nanocrystals via in-situ PL tracking and prove the formation of SCs in solution directly after the synthesis. We point out the importance of forming SCs during the cooling process is essential for higher quality NCs. We further proved the presence of SCs by using small angle x-ray scattering (SAXS) and wide angle x-ray scattering (WAXS) experiments and provide information on the SCs lattice structure. The optical properties of the SCs are characterized by time-resolved transient differential transmission (DT) and PL spectroscopy. Finally, we propose a qualitative model for the perovskite NC growth process.

2. Methods

Materials. All the reagents were directly used as received unless specified: PbBr₂ (99.999%, Aldrich), Cs₂CO₃ (99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich), 1-Octadecene(ODE, 90%, Sigma-Aldrich), oleylamine (>98%, Aldrich), toluene (99.7% GC, Sigma-Aldrich), Oleic acid (90%, Aldrich, degassed at 100 °C for one hour and kept in the fridge).

Design of in-situ PL tracking system. The PL data are recorded with a compact CCD spectrometer (Thorlabs, CCS200) using a fiber to collect the signal. The sample was excited by a UV LED flashlight (Fubosi, 100 LEDs, 395 nm).

Modification of the hot-injection set-ups. The hotplate is placed on a metal stand with adjustable height as shown in Fig. S1. The hotplate with heating covers when the temperature reaches the

desired temperature, the metal stand will be removed, after quickly injected the Cs-OA the hotplate will be exchanged with an ice-water flask for cooling down. The design is shown in Fig. S1

Synthesis of CsPbBr₃ NCs. In a typical synthesis of CsPbBr₃ NCs, 1.2 mL preheated Cs-OA was quickly injected into 0.207 g PbBr₂ dissolved in 15 mL ODE solution with 1.5 mL OA and 1.5 mL OLA at 180 °C. After 5s, the reacted solution will be put into an ice-water bath to cool down without stirring.

Characterization. The absorption and photoluminescence spectra were obtained by a Cary 5000 UV-Vis spectrophotometer and a Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies), respectively. The morphology of the NCs was characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) operating at an accelerating voltage of 80-100 kV (JEOL JEM-1011). High-resolution HAADF-STEM images were acquired using a cubed FEI Titan microscope operating at 300 kV. A probe semiconvergence angle of ~21 mrad was used.

X-ray scattering. The sample is placed in a monochromatic X-ray beam, and the scattering intensity is measured with a DECTRIS Pilatus 100 K detector for WAXS and Pilatus 300k for SAXS. The Mo x-ray beam energy is 17.478 keV per photon, which corresponds to a wavelength of $\lambda = 0.7107 \text{ \AA}$. The detector is mounted on a movable mount for a bigger scan area. To receive the exact sample-detector distance and to determine the exact location of the beam center, a reference measurement is used. Several images are taken from one sample to reduce background. For all calculations obtaining the radial scattering intensity profile, $I(q)$ from the final image, Igor Pro 7.08 and its macros IRENA SAS and NIKA SAS have been used with error calculation. The Q-range provided for WAXS-measurements is 0.4-6.0 \AA^{-1} and for SAXS-measurements is 0.03-0.5 \AA^{-1} .

Time-resolved PL spectroscopy. The PL decay measurement was taken using a Hamamatsu streak camera system (C5680). The sample was excited at 405 nm using a laser diode by PicoQuant (LDH series).

Differential transmission spectroscopy. A custom-built transient absorption setup by Newport Inc. was used. The sample was optically pumped using a 1 kHz femtosecond Ti:sapphire amplifier system (Libra HE+, Coherent Inc., pulse width ~ 100 fs) in combination with an optical parametric amplifier (OPerA Solo, Coherent Inc.). The same laser system in combination with a CaF₂ crystal, was used to generate a broad white-light continuum (290 nm to 10 μ m), which served as the probe beam. The change in transmission of the excited state with regard to the ground state ($\Delta T/T_0$) was probed at varying probe time delays using an optical delay stage (up to 3 ns).

3. Results and Discussion

To understand the formation process of perovskite NCs, we first set up an in-situ PL tracking system to detect the PL intensity during the hot-injection synthesis (**Figures 1 and S1**; for details on the synthesis see the Methods section). It is essential to stop stirring during the cooling process. With a UV flashlight shining on the flask, PL spectra could be acquired using an optical fiber connected to a CCD PL spectrometer. Full PL spectra (from 400 nm to 700 nm) are recorded every 100 ms during the synthesis. The result is displayed as a color map in **Figure 2a** representing the spectral evolution of the PL. At first glance, the spectrum redshifts with time. Two populations can be distinguished due to the asymmetric peak shape. The growth of the first peak at ~ 515 nm can be related to the formation of NCs during the initial cooling process. The second peak rising slightly delayed (~ 20 s) is more interesting since it potentially tracks the formation of superstructures or bulk materials. The PL intensity continually increases during the synthesis. The

SCs' peak position (529 nm) shows a slight redshift in the beginning and slight blueshift afterwards. To understand the shifting process in detail, we fitted the spectrum corresponding to a reaction time of ~5 s as an example using two Gaussian profiles, as shown in Figure 2b, the others spectra revolutions can be found in Figure 2a. The first peak (red) is located around 516 nm and attributed to the emission from NCs. The second peak (blue) around 529 nm can be related to the PL of SCs, according to previous reports.^{36,37} It should be noted that the formation of bulk perovskites during this synthesis is unlikely due to the steric hindrance given by the ligands.³⁶ In consistency with our previous report, the redshift of the PL relates to the formation of SCs.

According to transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of as-synthesized CsPbX₃ NCs (**Figure 3, a and b**), two different populations of products are present after the synthesis. Most of the NCs cluster together and form large aggregations causing a high contrast. A closer inspection of these aggregates reveals that they are formed by densely lying nanocubes (**Figure S2a**). Accordingly, superstructures form already directly after the hot-injection. The second population observed in TEM is given by small cubic structures (Figure 3a and enlarged inset). At a larger magnification, these small cubes appear quite monodisperse (see Figure S2b). Taking a look at a single smaller cube, as shown in Figure 3b and enlarged inset, a substructure containing many nanocubes becomes apparent. High-resolution scanning TEM images (Figures 3, c and d) show that the nanocubes are closely-packed within a single SC. We picked the smaller SC in order to get higher quality images. However, at the edge of the SC, some nanocubes are tilted or smaller in size. This inhomogeneous arrangement might be related to the size distribution of nanocubes directly after the synthesis. The individual nanocubes within the supercrystal (Figure 3 d) are stacked on top of each other, always leaving a gap in-between. As reported previously, such a structure could form during the drying process of sample preparation on a TEM grid.¹ However,

if we consider the extent of the high packing density of nanocubes throughout the sample, it is more likely that the SCs are directly formed during the synthesis.

To further confirm our interpretation, we then separated both populations by centrifugation. The corresponding TEM images and PL spectra are shown in **Figure S3**. At a low centrifugation speed, larger particles containing the superstructure of NCs form sediment and are thus separated from the solution. Interestingly, the superstructure remains stable in the sediment. This is in contrast to most of other NC synthesis approaches, where ill-defined aggregates of varying sizes forming during centrifugation are removed without inspection. To examine such phenomenon in detail, we diluted the as-prepared solutions without any further treatment in 1-octadecene (ODE) or re-dispersion of the sediment after centrifugation in toluene. A blueshift in emission was observed for both samples during dilutions(**Figure S4 a, b**). Therefore, NCs could be obtained by the dilution of SCs.

In contrast to the PL spectra, the absorption spectrum does not change after a slight dilution. Only in case of a dilution larger than 64 times, a tiny blueshift of the absorption onset can be observed (**Figure S4**). Importantly, the shift of PL peak and absorption onset is uniform retaining a similar peak shape. The remaining ligands in the solution cause a breakup of the nanocubes if the dilution is too strong as the fewer ligands on the NC surface can not maintain the stable NC structure. This yields either smaller NCs or nanoplatelets, which lead to the observed blueshift of UV-vis absorption and PL spectra (the blue shift as the previous report that diluting NCs will form nanoplatelets, thus also lead to the changing of absorption³²). This phenomenon suggested that a lower speed of centrifugation is favorable for the collection of higher quality NCs.

To further elucidate the distribution and arrangement of perovskite NCs after synthesis, we performed SAXS and WAXS experiments directly after the synthesis in the ODE solution and compared the results with samples obtained after drop-casting in a solid-state. We first evaluated the lattice geometry of the atoms within the CsPbBr₃ assembly. The possible lattice geometries for CsPbBr₃ reported in the literature include orthorhombic, tetragonal, and cubic.¹⁴ The Bragg peak positions for the three different geometries were calculated based on previously reported values³⁸ and superimposed with the data measured for a powder sample after background correction (see **Figure S5**). A cubic crystal lattice can be ruled out because of the mismatching of peaks (Figure S5a), while tetragonal and orthorhombic lattices both match reasonably well. According to previous reports, an orthorhombic lattice geometry has been found for CsPbBr₃ NCs with a similar hot-injection method, while a tetragonal symmetry was only detected at higher temperatures.³⁴ Herein we further confirmed this orthorhombic lattice geometry. The size of the nanocubes (**Figure 4a**) was determined to be 10.3 ± 1.3 nm by analyzing the peak width of the WAXS data with the well-known Scherrer-equation; the details of the analysis are shown in **Figure S6**. To probe the variation among different aliquots, different samples in either liquid or dry conditions were analyzed. No significant differences were found between these samples with respect to the crystal structure and the nanocrystal size (**Table S1**). Using SAXS, one can also probe the distance between particle assemblies in solution. The SAXS data show pronounced shoulders, which arise from the stacking of regularly shaped NCs into larger SCs. From those peak positions, we obtain a center-to-center distance of 11.3 ± 1.3 nm as shown in Figure 4b. This implies that the NCs of 10.3 nm size exhibit a spacing of 1 nm between each other, which is consistent with a ligand shell covering the surface of individual CsPbBr₃ NCs.¹⁶ Those ligands also give rise to a weak attraction between the NCs due to Van der Waals forces. Using the Scherrer equation again, we learn that

the superstructure assemblies have an average size of 30 nm (Figure 4c). This corresponds to an assembly of (at least) three NCs in each direction given a NC size of roughly 11 nm. As such, we find that on average 27 NCs form a densely packed SC cube (Figure 4d).

It should be noted that even larger assemblies may form in the ODE solution. However, those might have already settled down to the bottom of the measurement cell during the formation, which is beyond the detection of the X-ray probe beam. Future experiments with rotating cells are planned to clarify such a possibility.

To further prove the existence of SCs in the liquid phase, we prepared two samples containing either SCs or NCs and investigated them using time-resolved PL and transient DT spectroscopy at room temperature. For the SC sample, we used the as-prepared solution, while for the second sample, we diluted the SC sample by 100 times, which yields NCs as discussed previously (Figure S4). It should be mentioned that, as shown before, the SC sample contains a certain amount of individual NCs, whereas the NC sample might still contain some SCs as well.

For DT spectroscopy, the sample was optically excited with a 400 nm \sim 100 fs laser pulse. The induced changes in transmission were probed using a white-light laser pulse with a defined time delay. **Figures 5, a and b**, depict the observed DT spectra for NCs and SCs, respectively. In both cases, a strong positive signal at 500 nm can be observed, which can be associated with phase space filling at the bandgap transition. The corresponding time evolution of the signal at this wavelength is depicted in Figure 5c. The rise time of the signal can be correlated with the charge carrier cooling time. A monoexponential fit yields \sim 430 fs for both materials. After the signal reaches a maximum, it decreases slightly with a time constant of 55 ± 3 ps in both cases. We attribute this decay to non-radiative recombination caused by trap states. Accordingly, similar trap

states are present in both materials. Finally, the signal decays monoexponentially towards zero as the charge carriers recombine. However, the dynamics differ between NCs and SCs. The recombination process within SCs takes slightly longer (4.1 ± 0.15 ns) compared to NCs (2.6 ± 0.08 ns).

To investigate the different recombination times in more detail, we have excited the samples at 405 nm (low excitation regime) and measured the PL decay. In the case of SCs, the corresponding data are visualized as a color map (Figure 5d; for NCs see **Figure S7**). Since NCs and SCs exist in both samples but different amounts, we can observe a wavelength-dependent decay, which reflects both populations. The NCs dominate the short wavelength side of the PL peak, while the SCs emit on the longer wavelength side as the transition energy is reduced by miniband formation. As can be seen in Figure 5e, the PL lifetime increases for longer emission wavelengths. Accordingly, the electron-hole pair recombination rate is lower for SCs, which agrees with the DT data. Unfortunately, it is not possible to measure the QY of the SC sample as the concentration is too high, and dilution would destroy them. Thus, we cannot discuss if non-radiative processes play a significant role.

For NCs, electrons and holes are confined within a single nanocrystal. As the low dielectric constant of the surrounding causes only a weak screening of the Coulomb interaction between electron and hole, the result is a high exciton binding energy. This, in turn, leads to a high radiative recombination rate.³⁹ In SCs on the other hand, minibands are formed in both conduction band and valence band because of an efficient coupling between individual NCs within an SC. These minibands allow charge carriers to delocalize within an SC (Figure 5f). The formation of minibands is also observed by other publications. Moreover, due to the closely-packed NCs, the

increased dielectric constant resulted in a more vigorous screening of the Coulomb interaction.⁴⁰ Therefore, the exciton binding energy becomes smaller and thus, the recombination process slower.

As mentioned above, the formation and purification of perovskite NCs have not yet been fully understood. Most of the syntheses of nanomaterials discard the sediment, thus focus on well-dispersed nanoparticles.²⁸ Here, in the hot-injection synthesis of perovskite NCs, sediments are kept for further use, and this different process may have some hidden implications, which we aim to reveal. We argue that the SC formation during the synthesis process of CsPbBr₃ via the hot-injection method may further purify the product. As shown in **Figure S8**, the NCs exhibit a Gaussian size distribution directly after the synthesis. During the cooling process, NCs of similar size self-assemble into SCs, leaving smaller or bigger nanoparticles behind. By centrifugation with a low speed, only those self-assembled SCs are deposited as a sediment. After a few purification cycles, only high-quality NCs remain in the form of SCs. Conventional synthesis protocols suggest diluting the as-prepared solution directly after the reaction has finished. Therefore, the role of SCs remained undetected so far. We find that this self-size selection process leading to the formation of SCs is an essential step in the synthesis of high-quality NCs.

4. Conclusions

Using in-situ PL tracking, we discussed in detail the different stages during the synthesis of CsPbBr₃ NCs and observed the spontaneous formation of SCs in solution by SAXS and WAXS measurements. The optical properties of these SCs were discussed in terms of miniband formation and Coulomb screening by DT spectroscopy and time resolved PL measurements showing longer decay times for the colloidal superlattices due to delocalization of charge carriers. Finally, we

proposed a qualitative model for the perovskite NC growth via a self-size selection process where only high-quality NCs assemble to an SC.

Figure 1. Sketch illustrating the design of the in-situ PL and temperature tracking system.

Figure 2. a) Colour map illustrating the change of the PL emission during the synthesis. b) PL spectrum corresponding to a reaction time of ~5 s (black) fitted by two Gaussian peaks (red and blue)

Figure 3. a) TEM overview images of CsPbBr₃ SCs and b) an **individual** SC. c) HAAD-STEM image of an individual SC. d) High-resolution image showing the individual nanocubes forming a SC.

Figure 4. Arrangement of CsPbBr₃ NCs down to the atomic level as obtained from SAXS and WAXS measurements. a) The ions form an orthorhombic perovskite lattice with $a = 8.425$ Å, $b = 12.011$ Å, and $c = 8.370$ Å. b) Visualization of the ligands oleic acid and oleylamine comprising a non-polar chain and a polar head, which attaches to the NC's surface via electrostatic interactions. c) Background corrected SAXS signal of the sample (brown squares) and corresponding model (black line). The locations of the super lattice Bragg peaks are indicated by the black dashed lines. For better understanding, the first three fitted peaks are displayed. The dark-green lines mark the q-range within that the model was applied. d) Visualization of the concluded superstructure: 27 NCs from a 3x3x3 SC. These SCs also form larger aggregates on a disordered lattice.

Figure 5. DT spectra of a) NCs and b) SCs in toluene at various time delays. The pump wavelength was set to 400 nm. c) Comparison of the normalized evolution of the DT at 500 nm. d) Colour map representing the time-resolved PL of the SC sample in solution. e) Corresponding PL lifetime as a function of the emission wavelength. f) Scheme illustrating miniband formation due to coupling between individual NCs within a SC. The electric field lines are sketched as black lines showing the enhanced screening of the Coulomb interaction between electrons and holes in the case of SCs

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at
Detailed information about TEM, PL, SAXS and WAXS, Sketch illustrating figures.

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Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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Supporting Information

Growth and Formation of Perovskite Nanocrystals and Their Superstructures Revealed by In-situ Spectroscopy

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Figure S1. Schematic illustration of the stand modification for the hot-injection process. After hot-injection, we can remove the hot plate and start in-situ cooling with an ice water bath.

Figure S2. TEM image of the as-synthesized sample without any dilution.

Figure S3. TEM and PL spectra of hot-injection samples obtained as sediment after a selection process using different centrifugation speeds: a) 5000 rpm, b) 8000 rpm, and c) 12000 rpm.

Figure S4. Dilution effect on the PL and absorption of hot-injection samples in ODE (transferred into toluene after first centrifugation).

Figure S5. Comparison of the calculated and literature lattice parameters for a) cubic, b) tetragonal, and c) orthorhombic crystal structures.

$$\bar{L} = \frac{110 \text{ \AA} + 99 \text{ \AA} + 111 \text{ \AA} + 103 \text{ \AA} + 96 \text{ \AA}}{5} \approx (103 \pm 13) \text{ \AA}.$$

Figure S6. Calculation of the nanocube size

	LQ1	LQ2	LQ3	S8	S8d	S12	average	error
lattice parameter a [Å]	108	115	112	109	117	113	112	±12%
particle diameter $L_{m,cor}$ [Å]	279	258	325	317	304	304	298	±12%
particle radius R [Å]	142	182	180	144	144	151	157	±25
well depth ϵ [eV]	23	17	28	21	26	20	23	±8
packing fraction η (maximal 0.08)	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.08	0.07	±0.02

Table S1. Comparison of different sample batches (S8 is what we used in main text).

Figure S7. Color map representing the time-resolved PL of NCs dispersed in toluene and excited at 405 nm.

Figure S8. Schematic illustration for the self-assembly process.

